

EXPLORING BACTERIOPHAGE EFFICACY AGAINST PATHOGENIC
ESCHERICHIA COLI AND *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17411946>

Keywords

Antibiotic Resistance, Bacterial Lysis, Escherichia Coli, Phage Stability, Phage Therapy, Plaque Assay, Spot Test, Staphylococcus Aureus

Article History

Received: 31 August 2025

Accepted: 09 October 2025

Published: 22 October 2025

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Abstract

Background:

The increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) Escherichia Coli (*E. Coli*) and Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*) has become a major public health concern. Traditional antibiotics are losing efficacy, necessitating alternative therapeutic strategies. Phage Therapy (PT), a natural and highly specific bacterial control method, presents a promising solution. This study explores the isolation and efficacy of bacteriophages against these resistant pathogens.

Methods:

Thirty environmental samples were collected from hospital sewage, farm sewage, poultry farms, and urban wastewater. Phages were enriched using bacterial cultures and screened via spot tests and plaque assays to confirm their lytic potential. Bacterial inhibition was further assessed through qualitative turbidity comparisons. Additionally, thermal stability tests were conducted at varying temperatures to evaluate phage viability.

Results:

Phages targeting *E. Coli* were detected in 30% of samples, the majority from hospital, urban, and agricultural sewage, as well as fecal and manure sources. In contrast, *S. aureus* phage was found in 26.7% of samples, with notable occurrences in hospital sewage, urban sewage, and poultry environments. Phage activity was most prominent in hospital sewage, where 147 plaques for *S. aureus* and 32 plaques for *E. Coli* were observed, corresponding to titers of 1.47×10^8 PFU/mL and 3.2×10^7 PFU/mL, respectively. Among the environmental sources tested, *E. Coli*-specific phages were most abundant in fresh poultry manure, with 54 plaques and a titer of 5.4×10^7 PFU/mL, followed by farm sewage, which showed 42 plaques and a titer of 4.2×10^7 PFU/mL. Bacterial suppression was observed in cultures treated with phage, and thermal stability tests revealed that lytic activity peaked at temperatures between 20°C and 30°C, diminished at 40°C, and ceased at 50°C.

Conclusion:

This study confirms the strong lytic potential of bacteriophages against *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*, suggesting PT may be a viable alternative to antibiotics.

INTRODUCTION

Bacteriophages are ubiquitous viruses that parasitize bacteria, controlling their density in humans, animals and the environment. Phages are often regarded as natural antagonists of bacteria due to their bactericidal properties and remarkable specificity (1). Evidence for bacteriolytic activity dates to 1896, but it was not until Félix d'Herelle, a self-educated microbiologist in 1917, and identified bacteriophages as parasitic to bacteria. He named them bacteriophage, from the Greek, meaning "bacteria eater" (2).

PT, the process of employing phages for treating infections caused by bacteria, started in the first decade of the nineteenth century but declined after a decade, with research on the issue halting in the 1940s. Yet the widespread use of antibiotics brought an end to PT in many countries, and especially in the West. However, bacteriophages remained used as therapeutic agents in Eastern European countries for almost a century (3,4). The renewal of interest in PT occurred because of the increased global rise in antibiotic-resistant superbugs and the lack of new classes of antibiotics over the past three decades. There is now a possibility that phages will be an important tool in the fight against illnesses caused by bacteria that are resistant (5). Preventing resistant infections can be the distinction between life and death in critical care facilities, where patients continually fight for their lives. PT is no longer a futuristic concept but has become a life-saving procedure (6).

Compared to antibiotics, phages are self-replicating, less toxic, and highly specific—targeting pathogens while sparing the beneficial microbiome (7,8). Since phages tackle a particular group of bacterial strains while protecting the surrounding microbiome, the same features make them a promising treatment. Since their abundance in biosphere as natural organisms, their unique bactericidal mechanisms deserve more attention (8). While phages may self-amplify and break down biofilms, they provide special beneficial effects in bacterial infections as bactericidal agents. In the presence of bacterial targets, they replicate at infection sites and multiply, while in the absence, they are self-limiting. Phages are becoming an attractive alternative to antibiotics because they are less susceptible to cause bacterial resistance (9).

Because of this, lytic phage is usually preferred to use in PT (6).

However, the effectiveness of therapy can be lowered by phage-resistant mutants, but this can be overcome using a "phage cocktail," a combination of phages with varying host specificities. PT had been numerically optimized with the use of investigation into the rates at which bacteria mutate to become resistant (10). For them to be safe and have therapeutic promise, genome sequencing is essential (11).

E. Coli is a facultative anaerobe which is present in the distal intestines of humans and animals generally and contributes to digestion and vitamin K production (12). Intestinal and extra intestinal diseases are commonly caused by *E. Coli*. Intestinal pathologies include watery or bloody diarrhea, hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), and colitis. *E. Coli* is responsible for extra intestinal disease such as bacteremia, sepsis, meningitis, and Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs), causing 80–90% community-acquired and 30–50% of hospital-acquired UTI (13,14). ESBL (Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase) producing Enterobacteriaceae has spread globally since the ESBL gene was first discovered in the early 1980s and has become endemic in Enterobacteriaceae (15). Antibiotic concentrations may need to be 10–10,000 times higher than the least inhibitory concentration in order to adequately kill bacteria in biofilms (4,16). Similarly, *S. aureus* is a commensal organism that has emerged as a major human pathogen. In regions of Europe, the United States, and Japan, 40–60% of *S. aureus* hospital isolates are caused by the rise of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), a fast-changing and internationally significant resistance pattern (17). Concerns were further escalated by the rise of CA-MRSA (Community Acquired MRSA) with the VR (Vancomycin-Resistant) in the late 1980s; vancomycin became a principal treatment for serious MRSA infections (18). Oxazolidinones have been well recognized as last resort antimicrobial agents to treat infections caused by MDR Gram-positive pathogens, including MRSA, since 2000s. But now, resistance to Oxazolidinones, to linezolid and Tedizolid, is observed in staphylococcal species, with Coagulase-

negative Staphylococci (CoNS), like *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *S. aureus* (19).

PT imitates the antibacterial properties of medications by using particular virulent bacteriophages to target bacteria that are resistant to several medicines. MRSA infections have also been effectively treated with PT (20). Since phages do not significantly impact human or animal cells, they have a high degree of selectivity for the adsorption and infection of receptors on bacterial membranes, greatly lowering the possibility of adverse consequences (21).

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1. Preparation of bacterial strains

To carry out this study, six random samples, three of *E. Coli* and three of *S. aureus* were collected from Anwar Clinical Laboratory, Swat. These specimens were provided as pre-cultured plates containing isolates of the corresponding pathogenic bacteria. The use of pre-cultured plates was advantageous, as it ensured the presence of the target bacterial strains, thereby eliminating the need for time-consuming identification of isolates through prior culturing. Aseptic measures were strictly followed during collection to prevent contamination. Every effort was made during transport of the samples to ensure the viability of bacteria is maintained and to minimize contamination with other microorganisms.

1.2. Sample collection for Bacteriophage Isolation

For bacteriophage isolation, a total of 30 samples were collected. This included samples obtained from sources, such as hospitals, farms, rivers and ponds, potentially contaminated with animal and human excreta. Additionally, samples were gathered from various environmental sources, such as soil and fecal material from different animals and birds. All the samples for bacteriophage isolation were collected according to the standard aseptic protocols with some modifications. Liquid samples from sewage sources were collected aseptically in leak proof 50 mL falcon tubes. These samples were then transported to the Microbiology laboratory of RIU Malakand campus in an icebox for further processing.

1.3. Samples processing for bacteriophage enrichment

Liquid samples collected from sewage sources were placed on the bench top for 15 minutes to allow heavy suspended particles to settle at the bottom but for solid samples, additional steps were performed. They were first added in small quantities (about 3-5 g) to approximately 20 mL of normal saline in a 50 mL flask. Then mixed thoroughly and incubated for one hour at room temperature, after incubation, both liquid and solid samples were then processed with the same procedure. The samples were first mixed using a vortex mixer and then allowed to stand undisturbed for 10-15 minutes. After this step, approximately 15 mL of supernatant was collected from each sample either solid or liquid and first centrifuged at a low speed of about 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. After low-speed centrifugation, 10 mL of supernatant was recovered from each sample and now centrifuged at a high speed of 15,000 rpm for 4-5 minutes. After high-speed centrifugation, the samples were filtered using syringe filters first 0.45 μm and then 0.22 μm and further processed for the enrichment to obtain phages specific to species or strains of our interest.

1.4. Bacteriophage Enrichment

After 24 hours of incubation of the bacterial cultures, a single colony was collected using a sterile loop from each fresh culture of *E. Coli* and *S. aureus* strains. The collected colony was inoculated into Luria-Bertani broth in a glass tube. The tubes were then incubated at 37°C in a shaker incubator set at 120-200 rpm to ensure proper aeration. The bacteria were allowed to grow overnight for 12-16 hours to ensure they were in the log or exponential growth phase. To confirm the bacteria were in their log phase, optical density (OD) was measured at 550-600 nm. An OD600 of around 0.4 to 0.6 typically represents the mid-log phase. About 5 μg of the overnight-grown bacterial suspension was collected using a sterile micropipette and added to a 100 mL Erlenmeyer flask. To this, 10 mL of filtered supernatant and 10 mL of 2 X LB broths were added. The flask was then incubated at 37°C overnight for 24 hours under agitation at 120-200 rpm. After incubation, a portion of the enriched sample was transferred into a 2.5 mL Eppendorf tube and centrifuged at high speed (14,000 rpm) at 4°C for 10 minutes. After centrifugation, the supernatant was collected and filtered using a 0.22 μm syringe filter into a 1 mL tube to remove any cellular debris.

1.5. Spot Test verification for bacteriophages

A small amount of bacterial culture was mixed with melted soft agar (0.6% - 0.7%) that had cooled to approximately 45-50°C. The mixture was then poured onto the surface of a solid agar plate (1.4-1.5%) and allowed to solidify, creating a uniform bacterial lawn. About 1-4 drops of the filtered phage solution were transferred and placed on the agar surface at different spots. The plates were left undisturbed to allow the drops to be absorbed completely and dry. The plates were then incubated overnight at 37°C. After overnight incubation, the plates were examined for the presence of bacteriophages, indicated by the formation of clear zones or plaques at the sites where the drops were placed on the agar.

1.6. Double layer agar assay

Different bacterial lawns were prepared on LB agar plates containing; Overnight cultures of *E. Coli* and *S. aureus* (100 µL each) and about 100 µL enriched sample or serially diluted enriched sample (dilutions avoid overgrowth that can interfere with the results) in 3 mL of top agar (TA) or soft agar. Immediately after the addition of top agar, LB agar plates were swirled so that the mixture is evenly distributed. The overlay or top agar was allowed to solidify completely. After this, the plates were incubated overnight at 37°C. After incubation, the plates were checked for the appearance of plaques or clear zones, indicating the presence of bacteriophages in the enriched samples.

1.7. Plaque assay

Environmental samples were collected from various sources including hospital sewage, fresh manure, and poultry soil. Phages were extracted via filtration (0.22 µm), followed by soft agar overlay plaque assay. Host strains (*E. Coli* and *S. aureus*) grew to mid-log phase. Serial dilutions (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}) of phage lysates were mixed with 100 µL of host culture and plated on LB agar containing 0.7% soft agar. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours before plaque enumeration.

PFU/mL was calculated based on the dilution factor and volume plated.

1.8. Bacterial Growth Reduction assay

It is an important method to evaluate the lytic potential of phages, at the very first three flasks were prepared, each supplemented with 50 mL of autoclaved LB broth. A known number of bacteria were added to the three flasks. In one flask, phages were added at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 1, in another at 100 MOI, while the third flask contained only bacteria as a negative control. Then flasks were incubated with the continuous shaking of 120 rpm at 37°C for 24 hours. Every 2 hours, a 2 mL sample was taken from each flask, and its optical density (OD) was measured using a spectrophotometer at 600 nm.

1.9. Determination of Thermal stability of Phages

Microbes thrive at suitable temperatures, but like humans, they can tolerate a range of temperatures. Extremely high or low temperatures can halt their replication by disrupting enzymatic activity. To assess phage stability at a different temperature, 1 ml of LB broth was inoculated with a known titer of phage lysate and placed at 4°C, 25°C, 37°C, 45°C and 60°C for 1 hour. After a specified interval, they were withdrawn and brought to room temperature prior to double-layer agar technique. The double layer agar method was performed and differences in titer were calculated.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Subculture of *E. Coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*

Pathogenic *E. Coli* and *S. aureus* isolates were confirmed by MacConkey Agar and Mannitol Salt Agar, respectively. *E. Coli* produced smooth, circular, pink lactose-fermented colonies, while *S. aureus* formed golden-yellow colonies with Mannitol fermentation (Figure 3.1 & 3.2).

Figure 3.1: E. Coli colonies on MacConkey Agar showing lactose fermentation.

Figure 3.2: S. aureus colonies on Mannitol Salt Agar with Mannitol fermentation.

2.2. Sample collection for Bacteriophage Isolation

A total of 30 samples were collected from different sources and were processed for the isolation of

bacteriophages. The following figure shows the distribution of sources from which samples were collected (**Figure 3.3**).

Figure 3.3: Distribution of collected samples by source

2.3. Spot Test results by sample source

Spot tests confirmed the bacteriophage presence in 30% (9 out of 30) samples against *E. Coli* and 26.7% (8 out of 30) against *S. aureus*. Positive samples exhibited clear lysis zones, indicating active phages (Figure 3.4 & 3.5). Among the tested sources, hospital sewage showed the highest positivity for

both *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*. Village sewage samples tested positive for *E. Coli* but not for *S. aureus*. Fresh manure, farm sewage, and urban sewage exhibited phage activity against both bacterial hosts, while home chicken soil showed higher activity against *S. aureus* (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.4: Spot test showing bacteriophage activity against *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*.

Figure 3.5: Comparative spot test results for E. Coli and S. aureus.

Figure 3.6: Spot test results for E. Coli and S. aureus against each sample source

2.4. Plaque assay and titer determination

Small, well-defined plaques were observed on bacterial lawns following soft agar overlay plaque assay, indicating strong lytic phage activity. Plaques were most frequently detected in samples from hospital sewage, farm sewage, and fresh manure, confirming the abundance of lytic phages in these environments (Figure 3.7). Clear zones of lysis were

evident, and plaque morphology was consistent with that of virulent phages (Figure 3.8 & 3.9).

Plaque counts were used to calculate phage titers (PFU/mL) using the formula:

$$PFU/mL = (\text{Number of plaques} \times \text{Dilution factor Inverse}) \div \text{Volume plated}$$

For example, from hospital sewage against S. aureus:

$$\text{PFU/mL} = (147 \times 10^5) \div 0.1 = 1.47 \times 10^8 \text{ PFU/mL}$$

Sample Source	<i>E. Coli</i> Plaques	<i>E. Coli</i> D/F	<i>E. Coli</i> PFU/mL	<i>S. aureus</i> Plaques	<i>S. aureus</i> D/F	Volume (mL)	<i>S. aureus</i> PFU/mL
Hospital Sewage	32	10 ⁻⁵	3.2×10 ⁷	147	10 ⁻⁵	0.1	1.47×10 ⁸
Village Sewage	11	10 ⁻⁴	1×10 ⁶	-	-	-	0
Village Sewage	8	10 ⁻³	8×10 ⁴	-	-	-	0
Chicken Drinkings	-	-	-	13	10 ⁻⁴	0.1	1.3×10 ⁶
Farm Sewage	42	10 ⁻⁵	4.2×10 ⁷	11	10 ⁻⁴	0.1	1.1×10 ⁶
Hospital Sewage	6	10 ⁻³	6×10 ⁴	14	10 ⁻⁴	0.1	1.4×10 ⁶
Urban Sewage	15	10 ⁻⁴	1.5×10 ⁶	27	10 ⁻⁴	0.1	2.7×10 ⁶
Fresh Manure	54	10 ⁻⁵	5.4×10 ⁷	8	10 ⁻³	0.1	8×10 ⁴
Fecal materials	21	10 ⁻⁴	2.1×10 ⁶	-	-	-	0
Village Stream	5	10 ⁻³	5×10 ⁴	-	-	-	0
Poultry Farm Soil	-	-	-	7	10 ⁻³	0.1	7×10 ⁴
Home Chicken Soil	-	-	-	9	10 ⁻³	0.1	9×10 ⁴

These results confirm the presence of potent bacteriophages in environmental sources, particularly

in hospital sewage, which yielded the highest titers for both *E. Coli* and *S. aureus* phages.

Figure 3.7: Comparative plaque count analysis for *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*.

Figure 3.8: Plaque assay confirming bacteriophage presence.

Figure 3.9: Highest phage titer observed in hospital sewage samples.

2.5. Bacterial Growth Reduction by Phage Treatment

Phage-treated *E. Coli* and *S. aureus* cultures exhibited reduced turbidity compared to controls, confirming bacterial inhibition (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.11: Reduction in *E. Coli* culture turbidity after phage treatment.

Figure 3.12: Reduction in *S. aureus* culture turbidity after phage treatment.

2.6. Thermal Stability of Phages

Phage lytic activity remained stable at 4°C to 30°C, decreased at 40°C, and was completely lost at 50°C. *S.*

aureus-specific phages retained slightly higher activity than *E. Coli* phages at 45°C.

Figure 3.13: Lytic activity of phages at different temperatures.

3. DISCUSSION

There is now a growing interest in the use of bacteriophage as an alternative for traditional antibiotics due to the rise of MDR bacteria like *S. aureus* and *E. Coli* (22,23). In this study, 30 environmental samples were collected from diverse sources, including hospital sewage, farm sewage; poultry farm soil, human excreta, and urban sewage. Consistent with previous findings, hospital and clinical wastewater were identified as rich reservoirs of bacteriophages due to the high bacterial loads that drive natural phage evolution (21,24,25). Moreover, *E. Coli*-specific phages were more frequently detected in poultry environments, which is evidence from studies that such settings favor enteric bacteriophages (25–27).

Phages against *S. aureus* were more frequently isolated from hospital sewage, whereas *E. Coli*-specific phages were predominantly found in poultry farm manure and sewage. This distribution likely reflects the bacterial host abundance in these environments (25). Previous studies have shown that *S. aureus*-targeting phages are common in human-associated environments, while enteric bacteriophages are more prevalent in animal-related samples (4). Based on spot tests, bacteriophages were detected in 30% of the samples against *E. Coli* and 26.7% against *S. aureus*; positive samples showed separate lysis zones. Plaque assays exhibited distinct lytic zones on bacterial lawns,

which further confirmed phage activity. The highest phage titer was observed in hospital sewage samples, where *S. aureus*-specific phages exhibited over 150 plaques compared to 32 plaques for *E. Coli* phages. These findings demonstrate that the enrichment of virulent bacteriophages develops in hospital settings due to the increased bacterial burdens and antibiotic-induced selection (21,23). The bacteriophages' host range and lytic efficacy varies.

The presence of resistant populations of bacteria was proven by the fact that some phages induced turbid or incomplete lysis, while others caused complete lysis of the bacterial lawn. This is in accordance with previous studies that displayed how bacterial defense mechanisms involving restriction-modification and CRISPR-Cas systems influence phage-host interactions (28,29). Hospital sewage's phages displayed considerably greater lytic potential against *S. aureus*, which is in line with data that show phages specific to *S. aureus* usually form larger plaques with stronger lytic activity than phages that target *E. Coli* (30).

The most significant finding was that PT greatly lowered bacterial growth, as shown by lower turbidity in liquid cultures. Effective bacterial inhibition has been shown by the greatly decreased turbidity of phage-treated *E. Coli* cultures compared to the untreated control (31). Similarly, phage treatment lowered the turbidity of *S. aureus* cultures. However,

some treated samples showed bacterial regrowth, suggesting the emergence of mutants resistant to phages. This phenomenon is well-documented and remains a major challenge in PT. Phage cocktails composed of several lytic phages which target multiple bacterial receptors have been considered as a way to decrease resistance (10).

Phage stability at different temperatures is critical for its utilization in biocontrol and therapy. Our results showed that lytic activity completely vanished at 50°C, while it remained constant between 4 and 30°C and was considerably reduced at higher temperatures (40°C). *S. aureus*-specific phages had a somewhat greater heat tolerance than *E. Coli*-specific phages, sustaining around sixty percent activity at 45°C compared to *E. Coli*-specific phages' roughly fifty percent activity (32,33). This suggests that phages specific to *S. aureus* might have more structural stability, which was previously observed in phages that infect *Staphylococcus*. Phage storage and therapeutic applications depend largely on resistance to temperature, which highlights the significance of effective formulation procedures such lyophilization (33).

These results, aligned with other studies, demonstrate that hospital wastewater acts as a reservoir for phages, specifically those that target MDR pathogens such as *E. Coli* and *S. aureus*. The emergence of highly virulent types of phages is probably driven by the presence of bacteria that are resistant to antibiotics in these environments (21,24). Additionally, *E. Coli*-specific phages are more commonly found in poultry environments, which is in line with our findings that *E. Coli* phages are more often detected in samples linked to poultry. Still, the majority of *S. aureus*-targeting phages were discovered in hospital sewage, confirming the idea that human-associated settings promote the evolution of *S. aureus* phages (25,34,35).

Durability and resistance of bacteriophages continue to be a major challenge. The complex nature of phage-host interactions is highlighted by the development of resistant bacterial populations, evidenced by incomplete lysis in some samples. In order to improve efficacy and lower the chance of bacterial escape, phage cocktails must be constructed in light of increasing concerns over phage resistance in therapeutic applications (10). To improve PT against

MDR bacteria, research in the near future should focus on broadening the characterization of the host range, improving the stability of phages in formulations, and investigating the synergistic approaches.

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